

Influence of Supervisory Activities on Teachers' Instructional Delivery of Economics in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigated influence of supervisory activities on teachers' instructional delivery of economic in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Two objectives, research questions and null hypotheses respectively guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 279 public senior secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire tagged "Influence of Supervisory Activities on Teachers' Instructional Delivery of Economics Questionnaire (ISATIDEQ)". The instrument was designed on a four-point rating scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. The instrument was validated and a reliability index of 0.80 was obtained using Pearson r. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching and organizing of workshops as supervisory activities influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study concluded that observing of teachers in micro-teaching ensures that teachers are properly assessed to improve themselves and their instructional abilities. Supervisors' organizing of workshops stimulates the professional growth and development of teachers. It was recommended among others that educational managers should ensure that secondary school teachers are observed during micro-teaching in order to enhance effective instructional delivery in schools. Classroom managers should ensure that they attend workshops in order to be abreast with modern ways of teaching in the school system.

Keywords: Supervisory Activities, Influence, Teachers, Instructional Delivery, Economics, Micro-Teaching, Workshops

INTRODUCTION

Education has been known to be the antidote to poverty and ignorance and the key for unlocking natural resources (Obaji, 2006). Since education is accepted to be an instrument of change; teachers serve as the main operators of the instrument while the students are referred to as the raw materials to be processed on which the change would be manifested over a period of time (Adenaike & Adebajo, 2019). In an attempt to ensure that the value of education is being derived at all levels, some officials are charged with the responsibility to monitor the performances of all those who run education especially those in schools in order to find out or assess the extent of achievement of the goals of education. These officials are the ones officially designated as supervisors.

It is basic that the purpose of having supervisors in our schools is to control the quality of education received by our children. It lays emphasis on the classroom performance of teachers, especially on the duties assigned to them. With the huge amount spent on education yearly by the government, the parents would like to have a feedback to the success

or failure of the system where they have huge investment. In the school system, the supervisors are representing the interest of the government and from them the government has adequate feedback. In the school system, the supervisors are quality controllers. In the school, the role of supervisors is that of monitoring officers of the school programme (Olowoye & Alani, 2019).

Nwokafor (2019) saw the main task of the supervisor as that of creating conducive atmosphere for the teachers to be able to achieve desired changes in the learners in consonance with the peculiar needs of the environment. Supervision has its origin from the Latin word "super video" meaning "to oversee" (Adenaike & Adebajo, 2019). Therefore, supervision can be seen as a way of advising, guiding, refreshing, encouraging, stimulating, improving and overseeing certain groups with the hope of persuading people to desist from applying wrong procedures in carrying out certain functions on their jobs and at the same time try to emphasize the importance of good human relations in an organization (Akilaiya, 2018).

Supervision relates to guiding and coordinating the work of teachers and all connected with school work in such a way that students' learning is facilitated. The purpose of supervision can be classified into: Teacher Improvement Purposes and Non-Teacher Purposes.

Teacher-Improvement Purposes

1. Ensuring that teachers do their assigned work effectively
2. Ensuring that teachers are capable of carrying out their teaching responsibilities
3. Ensuring that new teachers receive training to enable them function effectively on the job
4. Ensuring that teachers are given assistance when they need it
5. Providing professional information to teachers who need it
6. Guiding teachers to the sources of instructional materials
7. Providing technical assistance to teachers when required such as in the preparation and use of teaching aids
8. Ensuring that discipline is maintained in the classroom
9. Maintaining high morale among the teachers.
10. Determining whether a teacher should be transferred, promoted, demoted, sent for further training, suspended, retired or dismissed for negligence and lack of productivity
11. Suggesting ways of improving the performance of incompetent teachers
12. Providing an opportunity to discover teachers with special abilities and or qualities.

Non-Teacher Purposes of Supervision

The following purposes which are not directly concerned with the teacher, also guide the Supervisor:

1. Ensuring the supply of teaching materials to the school
2. Ensuring that the quality of instruction is maintained in the school
3. Providing an opportunity to assess the moral tone of the school
4. Providing feedback to educational planners on the need for curriculum changes/improvement (Gurr, 2019).

Economics is one of the electives or group of subjects expected to be studied at the senior secondary schools level (FRN, 2014). It is taught in the secondary schools to allow students to understand today's economic environment. Alan in Ekweme (2021) asserted that economics is

concerned with how people, either individuals or groups, attempt to accommodate scarce resource of their wants through production substitution and exchange process. Robbins in Anyanwuocha (2013) posited that economics is the science which studies human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means which have alternative uses. Onwukwe in Ekweme (2021) opined that the study of economics is based on the fact that while human wants are unlimited, the means of satisfying them are limited in supply. To cope with this very unfortunate situation, man must economize, but cannot accomplish it without teaching and learning economics.

Supervisors organize micro-teaching for teachers to be effective in the delivery of economics as a subject. Micro teaching is very necessary for teaching both pre-service and in- service teachers. It is a teaching situation which is scaled down in terms of time, class size, and teaching complexity to allow the teacher focus on selected teaching strategy. It is designated to develop new skills and refine old ones. Depending on the availability of facilities, the lesson may be or not video recorded. After the lesson, the teacher together with the supervisor (and the pupils) will view the replay of the lesson, evaluate the person and discuss aspects of the lesson. The supervisor suggests ways by which the lesson could be improved.

Workshop is an activity that involves a small group of people that is temporarily formed to discuss a specific topic, or work on a common problem and trying to find solution(s) to a specific problem. Maximum emphasis is always on interaction and an optimum amount of critical analysis of ideas related to the problem or topic at hand is encouraged in a permissive topic-centered, face-to-face situation (Ogunsanju, 2016). The participants could comprise of teachers, supervisor(s), professional educators or resource persons and the theme of the workshop must either center on educational issues or instructional problems. Educational workshop could be organized at local school level or national level. The workshop must be planned so as to map out the venue, the purpose of the seminar, logistics involved based on the anticipated number of participants. There are certain features of educational workshop, they are:

1. Workshop must be held when all the participants would be available.

2. Workshop must be a reflection of obvious educational problem of teachers and other professionals.
3. It must have a leader, or a coordinator who presides over the planning of the workshop, controls the workshop, ensures attendance of all participants etc.

Evaluation is very important in workshops. A workshop without evaluation will not achieve much because, it is through evaluation that the entire values and results of the workshop would crystallize. This evaluation should cover the process of the workshop, the methods of cooperation and the learning outcomes. Evaluation results will help all the participants informed on gains of the workshop and highlights the need for further workshop.

Statement of the Problem

Instructional supervision is a constant process that aims at improving teaching by providing needed services to teachers. Improving teaching is a complex process in which many elements should interact. Teachers are at the centre of this improvement process. Their acceptance of instructional supervision and interaction with instructional supervisors provide the catalyst for any supervisory success. In an attempt to ensure that the value of education is being derived at all levels, some officials (Supervisors) are charged with the responsibility to monitor the performances of all those who run education especially those in schools in order to assess the extent of achievement of the goals of education.

However, observation has shown that supervisors hardly use supervisory techniques in the course of their visits to schools for supervision. Given that instructional supervision is a constant process that aims at improving teaching by providing needed services to teachers, the question is put: Do supervisors visit to schools to organize micro-teaching, and workshops influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis? Finding answer to this question becomes the problem of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine influence of supervisory activities on teachers' instructional

delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Identify the ways supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
4. Determine the ways supervisors' organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. In what ways do supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State?
2. In what ways do supervisors' organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors' organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 279

secondary school teachers. The purposive sampling was used to adopt the entire population as the sample size. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Influence of Supervisory Activities on Teachers’ Instructional Delivery of Economics Questionnaire (ISATIDEQ)”. The instrument was designed on a four-point rating scale response options of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point respectively. The questionnaire was validated and its reliability index established at 0.80. Pearson r was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument. A total of 279 copies of questionnaire were administered, but only 223 copies were correctly filled and retrieved. This was used for analysis for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research

questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In terms of decision, 2.50 was the criterion mean. Mean values below 2.50 were tagged “Disagreed” while mean values of 2.50 and above were tagged “Agreed”. On the other hand, when the z-critical value was higher than the z-calculated, the null hypothesis was accepted. But when the z-critical value was lower than the z-calculated value, the null hypothesis was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: In what ways do supervisors observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State?

Table 1: Ways Supervisors’ Observing of Teachers in Micro-Teaching as a Supervisory Activity Influences Teachers’ Instructional Delivery of Economics

S/ N	Questionnaire Items	Male Teachers (N= 98)		Female Teachers (N = 125)		Mean Set $\frac{\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2}{2}$	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
1.	Supervisors’ observing of teachers in micro-teaching enables teachers to improve the academic performance of students.	2.98	0.11	2.87	0.93	2.93	Agreed
2.	It ensures the implementation of appropriate implementation of up-to-date services.	2.86	0.20	2.94	0.90	2.90	Agreed
3.	It ensures that the teacher is properly assessed to improve in his instructional abilities.	2.99	0.19	2.81	0.90	2.90	Agreed
4.	It ensures that the quality of teachers is improved.	2.99	1.18	2.82	0.91	2.91	Agreed
5.	It makes teachers work effectively towards achieving school objectives.	2.96	0.70	2.85	0.68	2.92	Agreed
	Grand \bar{x} & SD	2.96	0.48	2.86	0.86	2.91	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024.

Table 1 reveals that the mean set scores in items 1 - 5 range between 2.90 to 2.93, which were above the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that the respondents all agreed that supervisors observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Research Question 2: In what ways do supervisors’ organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State?

Table 2: Ways Supervisors’ Organizing of Workshops as a Supervisory Activity Influences Teachers’ Instructional Delivery of Economics

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male Teachers (N= 98)		Female Teachers (N = 125)		Mean Set $\frac{\bar{x}_1 + \bar{x}_2}{2}$	Remarks
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
6.	Supervisors’ organizing of workshops updates teachers in new technique in teaching economics.	2.99	0.54	2.87	0.74	2.93	Agreed
7.	It provides teachers with new skills and a sense of accomplishment in the teaching of economics.	2.96	0.90	2.89	0.91	2.93	Agreed
8.	It provides an opportunity for the interaction that enables teachers to connect materials to the context of the learners in the teaching of economics.	2.94	0.11	2.87	0.51	2.91	Agreed
9.	It helps teachers to update their knowledge and be current in the area of teaching economics.	2.94	0.60	2.87	0.76	2.91	Agreed
10.	It helps teachers to disseminate new ideas and skills in the teaching of economics.	2.94	0.26	2.85	0.57	2.90	Agreed
Grand \bar{x} & SD		2.95	0.48	2.87	0.70	2.92	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Table 2 reveals that the mean scores in items 6 - 10, range between 2.90 and 2.93 which were above the criterion mean of 2.50 and therefore indicated that the respondents agreed that supervisors organizing of workshops for teachers as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors’ observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 3: z-Test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Teachers on the Ways Supervisors Observing of Teachers in Micro-Teaching as a Supervisory Activity Influences Instructional Delivery of Economics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Level of Sign	z-Cal.	z-Crit	Decision
Male Teachers	98	2.96	0.48	221	0.05	0.10	1.96	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female Teachers	125	2.86	0.86					

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Data on Table 3 reveals that the z-calculated value of 0.10 was less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 221 degrees of freedom and 0.05 significance level; hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors’ observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers’

instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors’ organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers’ instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Table 4: z-Test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Responses of Male and Female Teachers on the Ways Supervisors Organizing of Workshops as a Supervisory Activity Influences Teachers' Instructional Delivery of Economics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Level of Sign	z-Cal.	z-Crit	Decision
Male Teachers	98	2.95	0.48	221	0.05	1.01	1.96	Ho ₂
Female Teachers	125	2.87	0.70					Accepted

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Data on Table 4 reveals that the z-calculated value of 1.01 was less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 221 degree of freedom and 0.05 significance level; therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

On the ways supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, the study discovered among others that it makes teachers work effectively towards achieving schools objectives. The study also found that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors' observing of teachers in micro-teaching as a supervisory activity influences instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The results of this study support the findings of Ogunsanju (2016). However, the findings are contrary to that of Mbiti (2018), Adesina (2016) and Dienye (2014).

On the ways supervisors' organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, this study discovered that it update teachers in new techniques in teaching economics; it provides teachers with new skills and a sense of accomplishment in teaching of economics; provides an opportunity for the interaction that enables to connect materials to the context of the learners in the teaching of economics, etc. The study also found that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on the ways supervisors' organizing of workshops as a supervisory activity influences instructional delivery

of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The results of this study support the findings of Mbiti (2018), Adesina (2016) and Dienye (2014). However, Ogunsanju (2016) stated that workshop is an activity that involves a small group of people that is temporarily formed to discuss a specific topic, or work on a common problem and trying to find solution to a specific problem. Maximum emphasis is always on interaction and an optimum amount of critical analysis of ideas related to the problem or topic at hand is encouraged in a permissive topic-centred, face-to-face situation.

CONCLUSION

Supervisors' visit to schools to observe teachers in micro-teaching and organize workshops for teachers influences teachers' instructional delivery of economics in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The observing of teachers in micro-teaching ensures that they are properly assessed to improve themselves and their instructional abilities. Supervisors' organizing of workshops stimulates the professional growth and development of teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made by the researcher:

1. Government should ensure that school supervisors perform their supervisory roles in order to enhance effective teaching and learning of economics in secondary schools.
2. Educational managers should ensure that secondary school teachers are observed during micro-teaching in order to enhance effective instructional delivery in schools
3. Classroom managers should ensure that they attend workshops in order to be abreast with modern ways of teaching in the school system.

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